

It is All About Seeing Things in Perspective — Part II : Involutions, Perspectivity and Conjugacy on Cubics

Hussein Khayou

Department of Computer Science
Higher Institute for Applied Sciences and Technology
Distinction and Creativity Agency
Damascus, Syria
hussein.khayou@gmail.com
hussein.khayou@hiast.edu.sy

February 02, 2026

Abstract

Building upon the projective framework established in Part I, this article investigates the Möbius isogonal cubic and its inherent symmetries. We define this class of cubics using Möbius transforms and prove their invariance under polar circle inversions and isogonal conjugacy relative to the orthic triangle of an associated orthocentric system. The article characterizes general cubic curves within a projective framework based on the interaction between involutions, perspectivity, and conjugacy. By generalizing the properties of the Möbius isogonal cubic, we demonstrate via projective transformations that any cubic can be represented as a locus of points defined by involutions. Furthermore, we establish an alternative characterization of cubics as the locus of conjugate pairs viewed through a central perspectivity, relative to a triangle system and an anticevian configuration of four points on the curve. Finally, we explore the concept of triangle polarity.

Keywords: Ten-Point Conic, Twelve-Point Conic, Degenerate Pencil, Cayley-Bacharach Theorem.

This paper continues the investigation initiated in [1], where the theory of perspectivity and involutions was used to solve Alhazen's reflection problem. Here, we apply those methods to the Möbius isogonal cubic and broader conjugacy generalizations.

1 The Möbius Isogonal Cubic and Invariance Properties

Let us first consider the involution on Γ to be a Möbius transform \mathcal{M}_Γ . Since \mathcal{M}_Γ is an involution it will have after normalization the form

$$\mathcal{M}_\Gamma = \frac{mz + n}{z - m}$$

Let a, b, c, a', b', c' denote the complex coordinates of the points A, B, C, A', B', C' , respectively. Solving for m and n from the conditions $\mathcal{M}_\Gamma(a) = a'$ and $\mathcal{M}_\Gamma(b) = b'$, we obtain

$$m = \frac{aa' - bb'}{a + a' - b - b'} \quad \text{and} \quad n = \frac{abb' + ba'b' - aba' - aa'b'}{a + a' - b - b'}.$$

Then \mathcal{M}_Γ corresponds the characteristic involution of the complete quadrilateral $A_{A',BB'}$. Observe that m corresponds to the center of spiral similarity, namely the Miquel–Steiner point

of A, A', B, B' which is mapped to the point at infinity under the involution \mathcal{M}_Γ . Furthermore, c' cannot be chosen arbitrarily in this setting, since $c' = \mathcal{M}_\Gamma(c)$ is determined. Hence, the Miquel–Steiner point lies on Γ . Finally, note that the transformation

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{z}$$

serves as the canonical representative of this class of involutions. The isoptic cubic curves are a special case when C and C' coincide with the foci of an inconic of the complete quadrilateral. We call this class of cubics as Möbius isogonal cubics and will justify the naming shortly. Let $a, b, c, a^{-1}, b^{-1}, c^{-1}$ be the complex numbers corresponding to the points A, B, C, A', B', C' ,

Figure 1: Geometric configuration illustrating invariance of isogonal cubic under polar circle inversion.

respectively. Let Γ denote the cubic curve associated with this configuration.

Define M and M' as the intersection points of Γ with the x -axis other than the origin O , and let P and P' be the intersection points with the y -axis other than O . The complex numbers m and m^{-1} represent the points M and M' , which are real numbers whenever the intersections have real coordinates. Similarly, ip and $-ip^{-1}$ correspond to the points P and P' , which are purely imaginary.

Thus, we obtain an orthocentric system on the cubic curve defined by the pairs of points (P, P') and (M, M') . The points (P, P') are always visible, whereas (M, M') may be complex (not visible on the real plane).

Let $U = PM \cap P'M'$ and $U' = PM' \cap P'M$, represented by the complex numbers u and u^{-1} . Then $\triangle OUU'$ serves as the orthic triangle of the orthocentric system.

Let (Q, Q') be any involution pair of points on Γ , corresponding to the complex numbers q and q^{-1} . Hence, the cubic curve is fully determined by the following points where O' the point at infinity, namely the pair involution image of O

$$O, P, P', M, M', U, U', Q, Q' \text{ and } O'.$$

Define $H = QM \cap Q'M'$ and $H' = QM' \cap Q'M$, which form another involution pair on Γ , represented by the complex numbers h and h^{-1} . Recall that O is the Miquel–Steiner point of the complete quadrilateral M, M', H, H' , so both quadrilaterals $HOM'Q$ and $H'O'M'Q'$ are cyclic.

It follows that H' is the inverse image of Q with respect to the polar circle inversion centered at M , with power

$$MO \cdot MM' = MU \cdot MP = MU' \cdot MP'.$$

Thus, the cubic curve is invariant under this inversion. By similar arguments, the cubic curve is invariant under all four polar circle inversions centered at P, P', M, M' , respectively.

Let \mathcal{I}_P denote the polar circle inversion centered at P , and \mathcal{I}_M the polar circle inversion centered at M . Consider the composition

$$\tau = \mathcal{I}_P \circ \mathcal{I}_M,$$

which defines an involution on the cubic curve \mathcal{P} . This involution fixes the points M' and P' , interchanges the pairs (P, M) and (O, U') , and sends the center U to O' at infinity.

Consequently, there exists a Möbius involution associated with each vertex of the triangle $\triangle OUU'$. Thus, the cubic \mathcal{P} admits three Möbius involutions, each determined by a vertex of the orthic triangle of its orthocentric system.

Figure 2: Geometric configuration illustrating invariance of the isogonal cubic under isogonal conjugacy.

For any involution pair (Q, Q') , the lines OQ and OQ' intersect Γ again at a new pair (S, S') . The lines QS' and $Q'S$ meet Γ at the involution pair of O , namely the point O' at infinity, so these lines are parallel.

Let OU and OU' intersect Γ again at L and L' , forming the pair (L, L') . Let OO' intersect Γ again at N . Then we have the parallelism relations:

$$QS' \parallel Q'S \parallel UL' \parallel U'L \parallel MM \parallel M'M' \parallel OO',$$

where MM and $M'M'$ are the tangents to Γ at M and M' , respectively.

Note also that UM and UM' are the angle bisectors of $\angle OUU'$. Moreover, by Theorem 5.2 in Part I, the locus of T is a line passing through N . When $Q = U$, this locus line passes through the intersection $UU' \cap LL'$, and when $Q = M$, it passes through the harmonic conjugate of O with respect to M and M' , i.e., the intersection $UU' \cap MM'$. Thus, this line passes through N, U , and U' .

Additionally, by Desargues' dual involution theorem, the pairs (UQ, US') , (UO, UT) , and (UQ', US) correspond to an involution on the pencil of U . Hence, the involution corresponds to reflection across UM (or UM'), the angle bisector. Therefore, (Q, S') and (Q', S) are isogonal conjugate pairs with respect to the orthic triangle $\triangle OUU'$.

Thus, the cubic is invariant under isogonal conjugacy. Moreover, all the isogonal conjugate pairs (S, S^*) are perspective from O' the point at infinity.

It may be tempting to think that the nine points

$$O, P, P', M, M', U, U', S, S^*$$

with (S, S^*) forming an isogonal conjugate pair, uniquely determine the cubic. In fact, these points lie on an entire pencil of isogonal cubics. Each member of this pencil is invariant under isogonal conjugation with respect to the triangle $\triangle OUU'$. Furthermore, every isogonal pair is in perspective from the intersection point of line SS^* with the cubic (in our example the perspective point is point O' at infinity). Consider a projectivity Φ that fixes the two circular points at infinity and sends the point O' to a point P_r . Denote by

$$O_1, P_1, P'_1, M_1, M'_1, U_1, U'_1, S_1, S_1^*$$

the images of

$$O, P, P', M, M', U, U', S, S^*$$

under the projectivity Φ .

The new configuration corresponds to the reference triangle $\triangle O_1U_1U'_1$ together with the point P_r and its associated anticevian triangle formed by P_1, P'_1, M_1, M'_1 . By Theorem 5.1 in Part I, the isogonal conjugacy invariance of the cubic curve is preserved under Φ . Hence, the projected cubic remains invariant under isogonal conjugacy with respect to $\triangle O_1U_1U'_1$, and all isogonal conjugates are perspective from P_r . In particular, S_1 and S_1^* are isogonal conjugates.

Since projectivity preserves tangency, the points P_1, P'_1, M_1, M'_1 are the contact points of the four tangents from P_r to the new cubic. These points correspond to the incenter and excenters of $\triangle O_1U_1U'_1$, thus forming an orthocentric system on the curve.

Moreover, the pairs

$$(P_1, P'_1), \quad (M_1, M'_1), \quad (U_1, U'_1), \quad (O_1, P_r)$$

constitute involution pairs defined by the vertex O_1 . Furthermore, involutions can also be defined from the other two vertices, namely U_1 and U'_1 . For example, one may consider the pairings

$$(P_1, M_1), \quad (P'_1, M'_1), \quad (O_1, U'_1), \quad (U_1, P_r),$$

or alternatively

$$(M_1, P'_1), \quad (U_1, O_1), \quad (P_1, M'_1), \quad (U'_1, P_r).$$

If we consider the involution defined by the pair (O_1, P_r) , then for any point Q on the cubic we proceed as follows. The line P_rQ meets the cubic again at a point Q^* , which is the isogonal conjugate of Q with respect to $\triangle O_1U_1U'_1$. Subsequently, the line O_1Q^* intersects the cubic at a point Q' , the involution pair of Q . Observe the analogy of this reasoning with Theorem 5.2 in Part I.

2 Barycentric Analysis of Möbius Isogonal Cubic

Let a, b, c be the side lengths of triangle ABC .

Definition 2.1 (The Four Centers). The incenter and excenters have barycentric coordinates

$$I = (a : b : c), \quad I_a = (-a : b : c), \quad I_b = (a : -b : c), \quad I_c = (a : b : -c).$$

Lemma 2.2 (The Rectangular Hyperbola Conic). *Any conic passing through I, I_a, I_b, I_c has equation*

$$lx^2 + my^2 + nz^2 = 0. \quad (1)$$

For the conic to pass through $I = (a : b : c)$, the coefficients must satisfy

$$la^2 + mb^2 + nc^2 = 0. \quad (2)$$

This automatically forces the conic to pass through the three excenters as well. Since these four points form an orthocentric system, every such conic is a rectangular hyperbola.

Theorem 2.3. *Let U and U' be isogonal conjugates, and let*

$$O = \left(\frac{u_1+v_1}{2} : \frac{u_2+v_2}{2} : \frac{u_3+v_3}{2} \right)$$

be their midpoint. The conic \mathcal{H} through I, I_a, I_b, I_c, O has an asymptote parallel to UU' .

Proof. Let $U = (u_1, u_2, u_3)$ and $U^* = (v_1, v_2, v_3)$ be normalized barycentrics. Isogonality gives

$$\frac{u_1v_1}{a^2} = \frac{u_2v_2}{b^2} = \frac{u_3v_3}{c^2} = k,$$

so $u_iv_i = ka_i^2$.

Substituting O into (1) gives

$$\sum l(u_i + v_i)^2 = \sum l(u_i^2 + v_i^2) + 2 \sum lu_iv_i = 0.$$

Using $u_iv_i = ka_i^2$ and (2),

$$l(u_1^2 + v_1^2) + m(u_2^2 + v_2^2) + n(u_3^2 + v_3^2) = 0. \quad (3)$$

The direction of UU^* is represented by

$$P_\infty = (u_1 - v_1 : u_2 - v_2 : u_3 - v_3),$$

and since $(u_1 - v_1) + (u_2 - v_2) + (u_3 - v_3) = 0$, this is a point at infinity.

Evaluate the conic at P_∞ :

$$\sum l(u_i - v_i)^2 = \sum l(u_i^2 + v_i^2) - 2 \sum lu_iv_i.$$

Using (3) and (2),

$$0 - 2k(0) = 0.$$

Thus P_∞ lies on \mathcal{H} , so UU' is parallel to an asymptote. \square

Corollary 2.4. *The isogonal conjugate of P_∞ is*

$$S = \left(\frac{a^2}{u_1 - v_1} : \frac{b^2}{u_2 - v_2} : \frac{c^2}{u_3 - v_3} \right),$$

and S lies on the circumcircle of ABC .

Let L be the line through S in the direction of P_∞ . The center Z of \mathcal{H} is the second intersection of L with the circumcircle. For a rectangular hyperbola passing through the incenter–excenter orthocentric system, the isogonal conjugation agrees with the polarity induced by \mathcal{H} on points at infinity. Consequently, the polar of P_∞ with respect to \mathcal{H} is the line joining Z to its isogonal conjugate S .

Therefore, the points Z, S, P_∞ are collinear, and the line ZS is parallel to the direction UU^* .

Figure 3: Geometric configuration illustrating Remark 2.5

The center of the conic (1) is the pole of the line at infinity, hence

$$Z = \left(\frac{1}{l} : \frac{1}{m} : \frac{1}{n} \right).$$

Remark 2.5. Returning to the Möbius isogonal cubic, recall that this cubic is the locus of isogonal conjugate pairs (F, F^*) for which the line FF^* passes through the point at infinity P_∞ . Each pair (F, F^*) forms the pair of foci of an inconic of $\triangle ABC$ whose axes of symmetry are parallel to the asymptotes of the associated rectangular hyperbola. In particular, the major axis FF^* is parallel to the line ZS , and the center of the corresponding inconic lies on the rectangular hyperbola.

Moreover, the point P_∞ is the Möbius involution partner of each of A, B, C under the three involutions defined at these vertices. The point S is the common intersection point on the cubic of the four tangents to the cubic at A, B, C and P_∞ .

Remark 2.6. By leveraging Remark 2.5, we can provide a synthetic construction for an inconic of $\triangle ABC$ given its generalized Gergonne point G . First, we construct the cevian feet D, E , and F of the point G on the sides BC, CA , and AB , respectively. The center of the inconic is then located by intersecting the lines AM_1, BM_2 , and CM_3 , where M_1, M_2 , and M_3 are the midpoints of the segments EF, DF , and DE , respectively; this serves as an affine generalization for locating the center of an incircle from its points of tangency.

The axes of symmetry of the inconic are parallel to the asymptotes of the rectangular hyperbola \mathbf{h} passing through the incenter I and the excenters I_a, I_b , and I_c . According to Theorem 2.3 in Part I, let O_2 and O_3 be the reflections of the center O across the lines I_aI_c and I_aI_b , respectively. We define O' as the second intersection of the two circumcircles of $\triangle I_aO_2I_c$ and $\triangle I_aO_3I_b$. The center Z of the hyperbola \mathbf{h} is then the midpoint of the segment OO' .

By Lemma 2.2 in Part I, the asymptotes of \mathbf{h} are parallel to the internal and external angle bisectors of $\angle OIO'$. Finally, having determined the directions of the axes and the center of the inconic, we locate H as the intersection of the minor axis with the side BC and determine the foci by applying the focal circle construction detailed in Lemma 2.1 in part I. Applying this approach we can construct the Möbius isogonal cubic by letting the center O moves on the rectangular hyperbola \mathbf{h} .

Figure 4: Geometric configuration illustrating Remark 2.6

3 The Main Involution Theorem and P-Isoconjugacy

In the following we will extend the notion of isogonal conjugacy to define the P -isoconjugacy.

Theorem 3.1. *Let $\triangle ABC$ be a triangle, and let P and D be arbitrary points in the plane. Let $\triangle P_a P_b P_c$ denote the anticevian triangle of P with respect to $\triangle ABC$, and let $\triangle D_a D_b D_c$ denote the anticevian triangle of D with respect to $\triangle P_a P_b P_c$.*

Then the triangles $\triangle D_a D_b D_c$ and $\triangle ABC$ are perspective from a point D' , which we call the P -isoconjugate of D with respect to $\triangle ABC$. Moreover, D' is the common intersection point of the three conics defined by the sets of points

$$(P, D, B, C, P_a), \quad (P, D, C, A, P_b), \quad (P, D, A, B, P_c).$$

If the barycentric coordinates of P and D with respect to $\triangle ABC$ are

$$P = (u, v, w), \quad D = (x, y, z),$$

then the barycentric coordinates of D' with respect to $\triangle ABC$ are

$$D' = \left(\frac{u^2}{x}, \frac{v^2}{y}, \frac{w^2}{z} \right).$$

Proof. Consider a projectivity that fixes the vertices A, B, C and sends the point P to the incenter of $\triangle ABC$. Under this map, the incenter together with the three excenters form an orthocentric system, which we denote by

$$P, P_a, P_b, P_c.$$

Let

$$E = P_a D_a \cap P_b P_c.$$

By construction, the quadruple $(E, P_a; D, D_a)$ is harmonic:

$$(E, P_a; D, D_a) = -1.$$

Since $P_a A \perp P_b P_c$, the lines AD and AD_a correspond to the internal and external angle bisectors of $\angle EAP_a$. Hence D' is the isogonal conjugate of D with respect to $\triangle ABC$.

$$h(1, 1, 1) - h(-1, 1, 1) = 0 \Rightarrow e + d = 0.$$

Thus any conic through P, P_a, B, C has the form

$$a(X^2 - YZ) + d(XY - XZ).$$

This expression is invariant up to a scalar factor under the isotomic map

$$(X : Y : Z) \mapsto (YZ : XZ : XY).$$

Therefore, if D lies on the conic, then its isotomic conjugate D' also lies on the same conic. Repeating the argument for the other two analogous conics shows that D' lies on all three conics associated with the cevians through A, B, C . \square

Remark 3.2. In the context of Theorem 3.1, there will be a cubic passing through the points $A, B, C, P, P_a, P_b, P_c, D_a, D_b, D_c$ and D and D' . The points D_b, D_c and D will be the contact points of the four tangents from P to the cubic.

Figure 6: Geometric configuration illustrating Remark 3.2

Theorem 3.1 utilized barycentric analysis to show that D' , the P -conjugate of D with respect to $\triangle ABC$, is common to three conics. The following result strengthens this finding, demonstrating that D' serves as a common point for six such conics.

Theorem 3.3. *In the context of Theorem 3.1. A triangle $\triangle ABC$ accompanied with the anticevian system P_a, P_b, P_c for the point P , the six conics uniquely determined by the following sets of five points are concurrent at D' the P -conjugate of D relative to $\triangle ABC$:*

$$\begin{aligned} (P_a, P_b, A, B, D), & \quad (P_a, P_c, A, C, D), & \quad (P_b, P_c, B, C, D) \\ (P, P_a, B, C, D), & \quad (P, P_b, A, C, D), & \quad (P, P_c, A, B, D) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By Remark 3.2, there exists an involution on the pencil of lines passing through A , defined by the pairs (AP_c, AP_b) , (AB, AC) , (AP, AP_a) , and (AD, AD') . Consider the cubic \mathcal{U}_A associated with the point-pair involution mapping (B, C) , (P, P_a) , (D, D') , and (P_c, P_b) . By construction, A lies on \mathcal{U}_A as it satisfies the cubic involution condition for these pairs.

According to Theorem 3.4, \mathcal{U}_A is P -conjugate invariant, where all conjugate pairs are perspective from a point $A' \in \mathcal{U}_A$, the involutive pair of A . Since (D, D') constitutes an involution

Figure 7: Geometric configuration illustrating Theorem 3.3

Figure 8: Geometric configuration illustrating the proof of Theorem 3.3

pair on \mathcal{U}_A and is also a P -conjugate pair, it follows that A' lies on the line DD' . Furthermore, the tangents to \mathcal{U}_A at D and D' intersect at A .

By applying Theorem 5.3 in Part I, we conclude that the following four conics concur at D' :

$$(P_b, B, P_a, A, D), \quad (P_c, P_a, C, A, D), \quad (P_b, P, C, A, D), \quad (P_c, P, B, A, D)$$

Analogously, by considering the cubic associated with the complete quadrilateral $\{P_b, P, A, C\}$ and the pair (D, D') , we find that the subsequent four conics also concur at D' :

$$(P_a, A, P_c, B, D), \quad (P_c, C, P_b, B, D), \quad (P_a, P, C, B, D), \quad (P_c, P, A, B, D)$$

Finally, a similar construction for the cubic associated with the complete quadrilateral $\{P_c, P, A, B\}$ confirms that all six distinct conics are concurrent at D' . \square

Theorem 3.4. *Let Γ be a cubic curve, and let P_r be any point on Γ . Consider the pencil of lines through P_r . Let P_a, P_b, P_c , and P denote the contact points of the four tangents from P_r to Γ .*

The four points P_a, P_b, P_c , and P form an anticevian system with respect to a triangle $\triangle ABC$, whose vertices lie on Γ .

Let S_1 and S_2 be the intersections of any line from the pencil of P_r with Γ . Then S_1 and S_2 constitute a pair of P -conjugate points with respect to $\triangle ABC$ (as defined in Theorem 3.1). Moreover, $S'_1 = AS_2 \cap \Gamma$ and $S'_2 = AS_1 \cap \Gamma$ are also P -conjugate points with respect to $\triangle ABC$.

Additionally, the pairings (A, P_r) , (B, C) , (S_1, S'_1) , and (S_2, S'_2) define an involution $\mathcal{J}_{A,\Gamma}$ on Γ . The intersection $T = S_1S'_1 \cap S_2S'_2$ lies on the line BC . By the involution $\mathcal{J}_{A,\Gamma}$, the lines BC and AP_r intersect at a point A' on Γ .

Figure 9: Geometric configuration illustrating Theorem 3.4.

Remark 3.5. According to the construction rule given two pairs (P, P') and (Q, Q') derived from an involution on the cubic curve Γ , let $S = PQ \cap P'Q'$ and $S' = PQ' \cap P'Q$. These points (S, S') constitute a new involution pair on Γ .

Applying this construction to the pair (P, P') taken twice, we define $L = PP \cap P'P'$, where PP and $P'P'$ denote the tangents to Γ at P and P' , respectively. This implies that the tangent to Γ at P intersects the curve residually at a point K such that K', P, P' are collinear, where K' is the involution pair of K .

Consider the involution defined at A ; we have (B, C) corresponds to an involution pair, then the intersection $M = AA \cap BB$ is a point on Γ . Similarly, considering the involution defined from vertex B , where (A, C) is an involution pair, the tangents at A and B must intersect at the same point $M \in \Gamma$. By symmetry, the tangents at A, B , and C are concurrent at M .

The involution pairs of M under the three involutions defined at the vertices A, B , and C are the residual intersections of the side lines BC, CA , and AB with Γ , denoted as A', B' , and C' , respectively. Notably, the lines AA', BB' , and CC' are concurrent at the perspective point P_r . Thus, A', B' , and C' represent the P -conjugate pairs of the vertices of $\triangle ABC$ on the cubic curve.

Theorem 3.6. In Theorem 3.4. Let $G = AT \cap S_1S_2$ and $H = AT \cap S'_1S'_2$. The locus of G and H for involution pairs $(P_rS_1, P_rS'_1)$ on the pencil of lines through P_r is a conic \mathcal{C} passing through P, P_a, P_b, P_c and P_r . Moreover, Γ and \mathcal{C} have a shared tangent at P_r .

Proof. Consider a conic \mathcal{C} passing through the five points P, P_a, P_b, P_c and P_r . Define $A'' = P_bP_c \cap BC$ and $E = AP \cap BC$. Observe the harmonic bundles

$$(P_b, P_c; A, A'') = (P, P_a; A, E) = (G, H; A, T) = -1$$

Figure 10: Geometric configuration illustrating Remark 3.5.

Observe that from a point P_r , the tangents to the cubic Γ determine four contact points

$$P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4 \in \Gamma.$$

These four points form an anticevian system with respect to a triangle $\triangle A'B'C'$, where the points A', B', C' are the images of P_r under the three involutions centered at the vertices A, B, C .

We may now define the involutions at the vertices of the new triangle $\triangle A'B'C'$ and regard P_r as a perspector. The two intersection points of any line in the pencil of P_r with the cubic Γ then form a pair of P_i -conjugate points with respect to $\triangle A'B'C'$ where $i = 1, 2, 3$ or 4 . Furthermore, the tangents to Γ drawn from A', B', C' , and P_r concur at a new point $M \in \Gamma$. Thus the four points A', B', C' , and P_r constitute an anticevian system for a new triangle $\triangle A''B''C''$, from whose vertices we may again define the associated involutions. This construction process therefore iterates.

Figure 11: Geometric configuration illustrating Theorem 3.6.

Thus BC is the polar of A with respect to \mathcal{C} . Using Theorem 5.2 in Part I, there is an involution on the pencil of lines through P_r this pencil swaps the pairs $(P, Pa), (PS_1, PS'_1)$ and PA with the tangent to Γ at P . Projecting this involution from P_r to \mathcal{C} will produce involution points on the conic. However, every involution on a conic is a perspectivity through a point. In our case this point is A . Thus the lines passing through the two intersection points of $P_r S_1$ and $P_r S'_1$ with the conic will pass through A thus these two points are G and H respectively. Moreover, Γ and \mathcal{C} have a shared tangent at P_r . \square

Corollary 3.7. *Cubic curves can be characterized as the loci of P -conjugate pairs on a pencil of lines through a point P_r with respect to a triangle $\triangle ABC$.*

Remark 3.8. For example, consider the construction of the isogonal conjugate cubic perspective from D relative to a triangle $\triangle ABC$. This cubic passes through the orthocentric system formed by the excenters I_a, I_b, I_c and the incenter I of $\triangle ABC$. The tangents to the cubic at I_a, I_b, I_c , and I concur at D . Moreover, the tangents to the cubic at A, B, C , and D concur at D' , the isogonal conjugate of D . Any line ℓ passing through D intersects the cubic at two points, G

Figure 12: Geometric configuration illustrating Remark 3.8.

and H , which are isogonal conjugates relative to $\triangle ABC$. These points are determined by the intersection of the line ℓ with a conic \mathcal{C} , which is the isogonal conjugate of ℓ relative to $\triangle ABC$. The conic \mathcal{C} always passes through the points A, B, C , and D' . Furthermore, the three Cevian feet D_a, D_b, D_c relative to $\triangle ABC$ also lie on the cubic; thus, the cubic admits a D -conjugacy invariance relative to $\triangle D_a D_b D_c$. If D is a point at infinity, the cubic is a Möbius isogonal cubic.

4 Isotomic P-Perspective cubic and Barycentric Analysis

A special cubic \mathcal{T} arises when the curve passes through the vertices of $\triangle ABC$, the points A', B', C' and G (forming the anticevian system of the centroid G), and the points D_a, D_b, D_c and D (forming the anticevian system of a point D with respect to $\triangle A'B'C'$). Observe that it suffices for the cubic to pass through D and D_a to ensure it passes through D_b and D_c as well, because for such a cubic, the contact points of the four tangents from G are the anticevian system D_a, D_b, D_c and D . Thus, the cubic admits D -isoconjugacy relative to $\triangle A'B'C'$ perspective from G (i.e., all pairs of D -isoconjugates on the cubic lie on the pencil of lines through G).

The cubic \mathcal{T} is isotomic relative to $\triangle ABC$ because it passes through the centroid and its anticevian system. Furthermore, D' , the isotomic conjugate of D , satisfies $D' = AD_a \cap BD_b \cap$

Figure 13: Geometric configuration illustrating isotomic cubic part 1

Figure 14: Geometric configuration illustrating isotomic cubic Part 2.

CD_c (see Theorem 3.1). The tangents to the cubic at A', B', C' , and G concur at a point P where the line DD' intersects with the cubic. The point P serves as the perspective of the pairs of isotomic conjugates on the cubic relative to $\triangle ABC$. Moreover, let P_a, P_b, P_c be the cevian feet of P relative to $\triangle ABC$. These points lie on \mathcal{T} , and \mathcal{T} admits P -isoconjugacy relative to $\triangle P_a P_b P_c$. Additionally, the tangents to the cubic at A, B, C , and P concur at a point $P' \in \mathcal{T}$, the isotomic conjugate of P relative to $\triangle ABC$.

In the following, we will characterize this isotomic cubic as the locus of points Q such that the lines drawn from the Cevian feet of Q (Q_a, Q_b, Q_c) parallel to AP', BP', CP' are concurrent at a point of perspectivity $T(Q)$. Let X, Y and Z be the points at infinity on lines AP', BP' and CP' respectively. On other words the triangles $\triangle ABC$ and $\triangle XYZ$ are perspective at P' . By theorem 5.1 the locus of Q is a cubic \mathcal{T}' . The cubic \mathcal{T}' passes through A, B, C and P' . Let P_1, P_2 and P_3 be the reflection of P' across the midpoints of BC, CA and AB respectively. Observe

that there exist a point O such that the reflections of A, B and C across O are P_1, P_2 and P_3 respectively (see Theorem 2.3 in Part I). Thus, $G \in \mathcal{T}'$ as we have concurrency of the parallels at $T(G) = O$. Note, that P', O and G are collinear such that $P'G = 2GO$. Similarly, the vertices of the anticivian triangle $\triangle A'B'C'$ of G relative to $\triangle ABC$ are on \mathcal{T}' . Moreover, points P_a, P_b and P_c are all on \mathcal{T}' because we have concurrency at P_1, P_2 and P_3 respectively. This forces the two cubics to be the same $\mathcal{T}' = \mathcal{T}$. Since $P \in \mathcal{T}$ then it corresponds to a concurrency at a point $T(P) = S$ which is the reflection of P' across O . Note that we can pair the points $(G, A'), (P_a, P')$, by the involution from A , hence $S \in \mathcal{T}$. Moreover, $\triangle P_a P_b P_c$ and $\triangle XYZ$ are perspective at S . Additionally, we observe the collinearity of the triples of points

$$(A', P_1, P_a); \quad (B', P_2, P_b); \quad (C', P_3, P_c).$$

Let

$$P = (u, v, w); \quad \text{then } P'(vw, uw, uv)$$

The cevian feet of P on the sides BC, CA, AB are

$$P_a = (0, v, w), \quad P_b = (u, 0, w), \quad P_c = (u, v, 0).$$

Using homotheties at G we can compute O and S

$$O = (uv + uw, vw + vu, wu + vw)$$

$$P_1 = (-vw, vw + vu, wu + vw); P_2 = (uv + uw, -uw, wu + vw); P_3 = (uv + uw, vw + vu, -uv)$$

$$S = (uv + uw - vw, uv + vw - uw, uv + vw - uv).$$

Let Q_a, Q_b, Q_c be the cevian feet of $Q(x, y, z)$. The coordinates are $Q_a(0, y, z)$, $Q_b(x, 0, z)$, and $Q_c(x, y, 0)$.

The points at infinity (direction vectors) of the cevians AP', BP', CP' are denoted by points X, Y, Z at infinity:

$$X = (-(v + w), w, v)$$

$$Y = (u, -(u + w), w)$$

$$Z = (u, v, -(u + v))$$

We define ℓ_a, ℓ_b, ℓ_c as lines through the traces of Q parallel to X, Y, Z . Let (ξ, η, ζ) be the variable barycentric coordinates of a point on these lines.

The equation for ℓ_a (passing through Q_a and X) is given by:

$$\ell_a : L_1(\xi, \eta, \zeta) = (vy - wz)\xi - z(v + w)\eta + y(v + w)\zeta = 0$$

By cyclic permutation, the equations for ℓ_b and ℓ_c are:

$$\ell_b : L_2(\xi, \eta, \zeta) = z(u + w)\xi + (uz - wx)\eta - x(u + w)\zeta = 0$$

$$\ell_c : L_3(\xi, \eta, \zeta) = -y(u + v)\xi + x(u + v)\eta + (vx - uy)\zeta = 0$$

The lines ℓ_a, ℓ_b, ℓ_c are concurrent at a point P^* if and only if the determinant of their coefficients vanishes:

$$\mathcal{M} = \det \begin{pmatrix} vy - wz & -z(v + w) & y(v + w) \\ z(u + w) & uz - wx & -x(u + w) \\ -y(u + v) & x(u + v) & vx - uy \end{pmatrix} = 0 \quad (4)$$

This determinant \mathcal{D} expands into the equation of the isotomic conjugate cubic of P -perspectivity in terms of (x, y, z) .

$$ux(y^2 - z^2) + vy(z^2 - x^2) + wz(x^2 - y^2) = 0$$

Collinearity of $S, T(Q), Q$

If Q lies on this locus, there exists a unique point $T(Q) = (X^*, Y^*, Z^*)$ such that:

$$L_1(T(Q)) = 0, \quad L_2(T(Q)) = 0, \quad L_3(T(Q)) = 0.$$

Theorem 4.1. *Whenever $T(Q)$ exists (i.e., $\det(\mathcal{M}) = 0$), the points $T(Q), Q$, and S are collinear. That is, there exist scalars α, β, γ , not all zero, such that $\alpha P^* + \beta Q + \gamma S = 0$.*

Proof. Let L_i be the linear forms defining the lines ℓ_i . By the linearity of these forms, for any linear combination of points, we have:

$$L_i(\alpha T(Q) + \beta Q + \gamma S) = \alpha L_i(T(Q)) + \beta L_i(Q) + \gamma L_i(S).$$

We know $L_i(T(Q)) = 0$. Thus, for the point $\beta Q + \gamma S$ to lie on all three lines (making it coincide with $T(Q)$), we require:

$$\beta L_i(Q) + \gamma L_i(S) = 0 \implies \frac{L_1(Q)}{L_1(S)} = \frac{L_2(Q)}{L_2(S)} = \frac{L_3(Q)}{L_3(S)} = -\frac{\gamma}{\beta}.$$

We evaluate L_i at Q :

$$L_1(Q) = x(vy - wz), \quad L_2(Q) = y(uz - wx), \quad L_3(Q) = z(vx - uy).$$

Note that $L_1(Q) + L_2(Q) + L_3(Q) = 0$ identically. Similarly, evaluating L_i at S

$$\begin{aligned} L_1(S) &= (yw - zv)(uv + vw + uw), \\ L_2(S) &= (zu - xw)(uv + vw + uw), \\ L_3(S) &= (xv - yu)(uv + vw + uw). \end{aligned}$$

and summing them also yields $\sum L_i(S) = 0$.

Substituting our expanded results:

$$\frac{x(vy - wz)}{(yw - zv)(uv + vw + uw)} = \frac{y(uz - wx)}{(zu - xw)(uv + vw + uw)} = \frac{z(vx - uy)}{(xv - yu)(uv + vw + uw)}. \quad (5)$$

The vanishing of the determinant $\det(\mathcal{M}) = 0$ is the exact condition that allows these three ratios to be equal. When they are equal, $T(Q)$ is a point on the line QS . □

By Corollary 5.3, the locus of concurrencies $T(Q)$ of the constructed parallels corresponds to a cubic curve \mathcal{N} . The cubic \mathcal{N} passes through the vertices A, B, C , the points at infinity X, Y, Z , as well as the finite points P_1, P_2, P_3 and O . Moreover, the Steiner point S and its cevian feet S_a, S_b, S_c with respect to $\triangle ABC$ also lie on \mathcal{N} .

Conjugate pairs Q, Q' on \mathcal{T} are characterized by the property that (AQ, AQ') , (BQ, BQ') , and (CQ, CQ') form pairs of lines belonging to the three involutions on the pencils through A, B, C that define the conjugacy. When these involutions are projected onto the sides of the triangle, they induce involutions of points on the sides. In the case of isotomic conjugacy, these involutions correspond to reflections across the midpoints of the sides.

Recovering the conjugate pairs from the vertices of the triangle $\triangle XYZ$ yields conjugate pairs $T(Q)$ and $T(Q')$ on \mathcal{N} . Thus, $T(Q)$ and $T(Q')$ are conjugate points on the cubic \mathcal{N} , representing an O -conjugacy in $\triangle XYZ$. Finally, note that O is the common point where the asymptotes through X, Y, Z meet the cubic. Consequently, the line joining any conjugate pair $(T(Q), T(Q'))$ passes through O .

Remark 4.2. If instead we choose arbitrary points X, Y, Z such that the triangles $\triangle XYZ$ and $\triangle ABC$ are perspective from the point P' , then the resulting two cubics are projectively similar. In this more general setting the induced conjugacy is no longer the isotomic conjugacy, although the fundamental collinearity relation among S, Q , and $T(Q)$ remains preserved.

Remark 4.3. The general formula for $P_r(P_x, P_y, P_z)$ perspective cubic with $I(I_x, I_y, I_z)$ -conjugacy is

$$\sum_{cyclic} P_x x (I_z^2 y^2 - I_y^2 z^2) = 0$$

The tangents at A, B, C and P_r concurs at $P' = (I_x^2 vw, I_y^2 uw, I_z^2 uv)$ the I -conjugate of P_r .

Figure 15: Geometric configuration illustrating Remark 4.2.

5 Cubic as A locus of perspectivity

Theorem 5.1. *Given a reference triangle ABC , a variable point Q , and the cevian-foot triangle $A'B'C'$ of Q , the locus of points Q for which $A'B'C'$ is perspective with a fixed triangle XYZ is a cubic curve.*

Proof. Using barycentric coordinates, we show that the locus is a cubic curve, and we derive an explicit homogeneous cubic equation for this locus.

Setup

Let ABC be the reference triangle. Let the fixed triangle XYZ have barycentric coordinates

$$X = (x_X : y_X : z_X), \quad Y = (x_Y : y_Y : z_Y), \quad Z = (x_Z : y_Z : z_Z).$$

Let the variable point be

$$Q = (u : v : w).$$

The cevian-foot (trace) triangle $A'B'C'$ of Q with respect to ABC has vertices

$$A' = (0 : v : w), \quad B' = (u : 0 : w), \quad C' = (u : v : 0).$$

In barycentric coordinates, the line through two points

$$P = (p_1 : p_2 : p_3), \quad Q = (q_1 : q_2 : q_3)$$

has equation

$$\begin{vmatrix} x & y & z \\ p_1 & p_2 & p_3 \\ q_1 & q_2 & q_3 \end{vmatrix} = 0.$$

Thus, the three lines joining corresponding vertices are:

Line XA'

$$\ell_1 = \begin{vmatrix} x & y & z \\ x_X & y_X & z_X \\ 0 & v & w \end{vmatrix} = 0,$$

which expands to

$$\ell_1(x, y, z) = (y_X w - z_X v) x - x_X w y + x_X v z.$$

Hence

$$(a_1, b_1, c_1) = (y_X w - z_X v, -x_X w, x_X v).$$

Line YB'

$$\ell_2 = \begin{vmatrix} x & y & z \\ x_Y & y_Y & z_Y \\ u & 0 & w \end{vmatrix} = 0,$$

which expands to

$$\ell_2(x, y, z) = y_Y w x + (z_Y u - x_Y w) y - y_Y u z.$$

Hence

$$(a_2, b_2, c_2) = (y_Y w, z_Y u - x_Y w, -y_Y u).$$

Line ZC'

$$\ell_3 = \begin{vmatrix} x & y & z \\ x_Z & y_Z & z_Z \\ u & v & 0 \end{vmatrix} = 0,$$

which expands to

$$\ell_3(x, y, z) = -z_Z v x + z_Z u y + (x_Z v - y_Z u) z.$$

Hence

$$(a_3, b_3, c_3) = (-z_Z v, z_Z u, x_Z v - y_Z u).$$

The triangles $A'B'C'$ and XYZ are perspective if and only if the three lines ℓ_1, ℓ_2, ℓ_3 are concurrent. In barycentric coordinates, three lines

$$a_i x + b_i y + c_i z = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3,$$

are concurrent if and only if

$$\det \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & b_1 & c_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 & c_2 \\ a_3 & b_3 & c_3 \end{pmatrix} = 0.$$

Substituting the coefficients computed above, we obtain the homogeneous cubic equation

$$F(u, v, w) = \det \begin{pmatrix} y_X w - z_X v & -x_X w & x_X v \\ y_Y w & z_Y u - x_Y w & -y_Y u \\ -z_Z v & z_Z u & x_Z v - y_Z u \end{pmatrix} = 0.$$

Thus, the locus of points $Q = (u : v : w)$ such that the cevian-foot triangle $A'B'C'$ of Q is perspective with the fixed triangle XYZ is a cubic curve given by the equation

$$F(u, v, w) = 0.$$

□

Theorem 5.1 can be generalized as follows.

Theorem 5.2. *Let ABC be a fixed reference triangle and let l_1, l_2, l_3 be three fixed lines in general position in the plane. Let X, Y, Z be three fixed points in general position, forming a triangle XYZ .*

For a variable point Q , define

$$A' = AQ \cap l_1, \quad B' = BQ \cap l_2, \quad C' = CQ \cap l_3.$$

The locus of points Q such that the triangles $A'B'C'$ and XYZ are perspective, i.e.

$$XA', YB', ZC' \quad \text{are concurrent.}$$

is a plane cubic.

We Work in barycentric coordinates with respect to triangle ABC . Let

$$A = (1 : 0 : 0), \quad B = (0 : 1 : 0), \quad C = (0 : 0 : 1),$$

and let

$$Q = (x : y : z)$$

be a variable point.

Write the equations of the fixed lines as

$$l_1 : \alpha_1 x + \beta_1 y + \gamma_1 z = 0,$$

$$l_2 : \alpha_2 x + \beta_2 y + \gamma_2 z = 0,$$

$$l_3 : \alpha_3 x + \beta_3 y + \gamma_3 z = 0.$$

Coordinates of A', B', C'

The line AQ consists of points of the form

$$(t : y : z).$$

Imposing the condition that this point lies on l_1 , we obtain

$$\alpha_1 t + \beta_1 y + \gamma_1 z = 0,$$

hence

$$t = -\frac{\beta_1 y + \gamma_1 z}{\alpha_1}.$$

Therefore,

$$A' = (-(\beta_1 y + \gamma_1 z) : \alpha_1 y : \alpha_1 z).$$

Similarly,

$$B' = (\beta_2 x : -(\alpha_2 x + \gamma_2 z) : \beta_2 z),$$

$$C' = (\gamma_3 x : \gamma_3 y : -(\alpha_3 x + \beta_3 y)).$$

Each coordinate of A', B', C' is linear in (x, y, z) .

Perspectivity condition

Let

$$X = (x_1 : y_1 : z_1), \quad Y = (x_2 : y_2 : z_2), \quad Z = (x_3 : y_3 : z_3),$$

and

$$A' = (A'_x : A'_y : A'_z), \quad B' = (B'_x : B'_y : B'_z), \quad C' = (C'_x : C'_y : C'_z).$$

The line XA' has barycentric equation

$$d_1 x + d_2 y + d_3 z = 0,$$

where

$$(d_1, d_2, d_3) = (y_1 A'_z - z_1 A'_y, z_1 A'_x - x_1 A'_z, x_1 A'_y - y_1 A'_x).$$

Similarly, the lines YB' and ZC' have equations

$$e_1 x + e_2 y + e_3 z = 0, \quad f_1 x + f_2 y + f_3 z = 0,$$

with

$$(e_1, e_2, e_3) = (y_2 B'_z - z_2 B'_y, z_2 B'_x - x_2 B'_z, x_2 B'_y - y_2 B'_x),$$

$$(f_1, f_2, f_3) = (y_3 C'_z - z_3 C'_y, z_3 C'_x - x_3 C'_z, x_3 C'_y - y_3 C'_x).$$

The three lines XA' , YB' , ZC' are concurrent if and only if their coefficient vectors are linearly dependent, i.e.

$$\det \begin{pmatrix} d_1 & d_2 & d_3 \\ e_1 & e_2 & e_3 \\ f_1 & f_2 & f_3 \end{pmatrix} = 0.$$

Substituting the explicit coordinates

$$\begin{aligned} A' &= (-(\beta_1 y + \gamma_1 z) : \alpha_1 y : \alpha_1 z), \\ B' &= (\beta_2 x : -(\alpha_2 x + \gamma_2 z) : \beta_2 z), \\ C' &= (\gamma_3 x : \gamma_3 y : -(\alpha_3 x + \beta_3 y)), \end{aligned}$$

Degree of the locus

Each entry of the rows corresponding to A' , B' , C' is linear in (x, y, z) . The determinant expands as a sum of products of three such linear factors.

Therefore, the resulting equation is a homogeneous polynomial of degree 3 in (x, y, z) .

Corollary 5.3. *The locus of points of perspectivity in Theorem between the triangles $\triangle XYZ$ and $\triangle A'B'C'$ is another cubic.*

Note that Corollary 5.3 is the same as Theorem 5.2 but we are swapping the reference triangle from $\triangle ABC$ to $\triangle XYZ$.

6 Connecting the Dots

Theorem 6.1. *Let $\triangle ABC$ be a triangle, and let P be an arbitrary point. Define D, E, F as the feet of the cevians AP, BP , and CP , respectively. Let X, Y, Z denote the Miquel–Steiner points of the complete quadrilaterals $P_{A,BC}, P_{B,CA}$, and $P_{C,AB}$, respectively. Let P' be the Miquel point, i.e. the common intersection of the circles $(AEF), (BFD)$, and (CDF) .*

Then the nine circles

$$(BXC), (CYA), (AZB), (APX), (BPY), (CPZ), (AP'D), (BP'E), (CP'F)$$

are concurrent.

Proof. Consider τ_X the characteristic involution for the complete quadrilateral $P_{A,BC}$ defined in the proof of Theorem 1.1 in Part I. Line AP is mapped to the circle (APX) and line BC is mapped to the circle (BXC) . Hence, the circles (APX) and (BXC) intersect at a point H such that D is mapped to H . Since Y is mapped to Z (see Corollary 2.4 in Part I). Then the circles $(CDPY)$ and $(BAYD)$ will be mapped to the circles $(AZBH)$ and $(CPZH)$ respectively. Similarly, we find that the circles

$$(BXC), (CYA), (AZB), (APX), (BPY), \text{ and } (CPZ)$$

are concurrent at H .

Consider an arbitrary inversion centered at H . The mapping with respect to this inversion will be as follows: $A \mapsto A', B \mapsto B', C \mapsto C', X \mapsto X', Y \mapsto Y', Z \mapsto Z', D \mapsto D', E \mapsto E', F \mapsto F'$ and $P \mapsto P''$. By Corollary 2.4 in Part I, there exists a point O such that lines AX, BY and CZ are concurrent at O and O lies also on the circles $(AYZ), (BZX)$ and (CXY) . By the inversion, all the circles that pass through H will become straight lines, and all the lines that do not pass through H will become circles that pass through H . Moreover, X', Y' and Z' will be the feet of the cevian of the point P'' in the triangle $\triangle A'B'C'$. In addition, D', E' and F' will become the Miquel–Steiner points of $P''_{A',B'C'}, P''_{B',C'A'}$ and $P''_{C',A'B'}$ respectively. Applying Corollary 2.4 in Part I again, we get that lines $A'D', B'E'$, and $C'F'$ and the circles $(A'E'F')$,

Figure 16: Geometric configuration for Theorem 6.1.

Figure 17: Geometric configuration for Theorem 6.2.

$(B'F'D')$ and $(C'D'E')$ are concurrent at a point M' . Then M' is mapped to the Miquel point P' by the inversion and the circles $(AP'D)$, $(BP'E)$, and $(CP'F)$ concur also at H .

□

Remark 6.2. In Theorem 6.1, let \mathcal{M} denote the Möbius isogonal cubic with vertices X, Y , and Z comprising the centers of the three Möbius involutions. It follows that the incenter I and the excenters I_x, I_y, I_z of $\triangle XYZ$ lie on \mathcal{M} , thereby forming an orthocentric system on the cubic.

Consider the Möbius involution centered at X . This transformation induces the pairings (P, A) , (B, C) , (Y, Z) , and (D, H) . Similarly, H is paired with E and F under the involutions centered at Y and Z , respectively. We observe that the set of points $\{A, B, C, P\}$ constitutes the anticevian system of $\{D, E, F\}$. Consequently, we may define analogous involutions centered at the vertices of $\triangle DEF$. Furthermore, the lines HA, HB, HC , and HP are all tangent to the cubic \mathcal{M} .

Additionally, the pairs (P, A) , (P, B) , and (P, C) correspond to the involutions centered

at X, Y , and Z . Thus, the isogonal conjugate of P with respect to $\triangle XYZ$ is the point of concurrency, O' , of the lines AX, BY , and CZ , which implies $O' \in \mathcal{M}$.

Recall that Theorem 6.1 establishes the collinearity of H, O' , and P' , where P' is the Miquel point of the circles (AFE) , (BFD) , and (CED) . Let us apply an inversion centered at P' , which maps all circles passing through P' to lines. Let A', B', C', D', E', F' , and H' denote the respective images of the original points under this inversion. In this transformed configuration, $\triangle A'B'C'$ becomes the cevian triangle of H' with respect to $\triangle D'E'F'$.

By Desargues' Dual Involution Theorem, there exists an involution on the pencil of lines through P' that pairs the lines $(P'D', P'H')$, $(P'E', P'F')$, and $(P'B', P'C')$. Consequently, the point pairs (D, H) , (E, F) , and (B, C) are in involution within the pencil through P' , implying that $P' \in \mathcal{M}$. Thus, P' is the P -conjugate of O' with respect to $\triangle DEF$.

Figure 18: Geometric configuration for Concurrency in the circumcenter of $\triangle ABC$.

By virtue of P -conjugacy, the anticevian triangle $\triangle O_1O_2O_3$ of O' relative to $\triangle ABC$ is perspective with $\triangle DEF$ from the center P' . As established in Theorem 6.1, O' is the intersection of circles (BZX) , (CYX) , and (AYZ) , while P' is the intersection of (BFD) , (CED) , and (AFE) . It follows that O_1 has equal power with respect to the circles (BFD) and (CED) , as well as having equal power with respect to the circles (BFD) and (CED) . Since $\triangle ABC$ is inscribed in $\triangle O_1O_2O_3$ and P' (the Miquel point) serves as the perspector of $\triangle O_1O_2O_3$ and $\triangle ABC$, the point O_1 must be the radical center of the circles (CED) , (BFD) , and (ABC) . To justify the previous claim, assume that O_1 is not the radical center. Consider instead the point $Q_1 \in P'D$, defined as the radical center of the three circles (CED) , (BFD) , and (ABC) . By definition, Q_1 lies on both the radical axis of (BFD) and (ABC) , and on the radical axis of (CED) and (ABC) .

Define

$$Q_2 = Q_1C \cap P'E, \quad Q_3 = Q_1C \cap PF.$$

Then Q_2 is the radical center of the circles (AFE) , (CDE) , and (ABC) ; similarly, Q_3 is the radical center of (AFE) , (BFD) , and (ABC) . Consequently, the points Q_2, A, Q_3 are collinear, since they lie on the radical axis of (AFE) and (ABC) .

Let

$$D_1 = BC \cap Q_2Q_3, \quad D_2 = BC \cap O_2O_3.$$

Applying the Desargues Dual Involution Theorem to the quadrilaterals O_2B, O_1D_2 and Q_2B, Q_1D_1

from the center P' , we obtain the same involution determined by the pairs

$$(P'B, P'E), \quad (P'C, P'F).$$

Hence the pairs $(P'D, P'D_1)$ and $(P'D, P'D_2)$ correspond to the same involution, which implies $D_1 = D_2$. This forces $Q_2 = O_2$ and $Q_3 = O_3$, and therefore $O_1 = Q_1$.

Thus O_1 has the same power with respect to the circles (BZX) , (CYX) , (BFD) , (CED) , and (ABC) . It follows that the circles (BZX) , (BFD) , and (ABC) are coaxial. The centers of coaxial circles are collinear, and in particular the circles intersect in two points on O_3O_1 , one of which is B .

By an analogous argument, the three lines joining the centers of the circle pairs

$$\{(BZX), (BFD)\}, \quad \{(CYX), (CED)\}, \quad \{(AZY), (AED)\}$$

are concurrent at X_3 , the circumcenter of $\triangle ABC$.

Finally, consider the line passing through H directed toward the point at infinity (corresponding to the involution pair of X, Y, Z). This line intersects \mathcal{M} at H^* , the isogonal conjugate of H with respect to $\triangle XYZ$. It follows that the lines XD, YE , and FZ concur at $H^* \in \mathcal{M}$. Furthermore, $HH^* \parallel O'P$, as all pairs of isogonal conjugates on \mathcal{M} are perspective from the point at infinity.

Remark 6.3. A special case is when P in Theorem 6.1 and Remark 6.2 is the centroid. Then P' the Miquel's point will be the circumcenter of $\triangle ABC$. The cubic in this case will be Möbius isogonal relative $\triangle XYZ$ and isotomic invariant relative to $\triangle DEF$. Thus P' and O' will be isotomic conjugates in this case relative to $\triangle DEF$. Moreover, the circle (ABC) will now be the incircle of $\triangle O_1O_2O_3$.

7 Triangle Polarity and Triangle Inversion

7.1 Intuition and Setup

Our barycentric analysis motivates the introduction of two related concepts: *triangle polarity* and *triangle inversion*.

In Cartesian coordinates, the polar of a point $P(x_0, y_0)$ with respect to a circle centered at the origin with radius r is given by

$$x_0x + y_0y = r^2.$$

Earlier attempts to define a triangle polar of a point $P(u, v, w)$ relative to $\triangle ABC$ considered the Desargues axis of perspectivity between $\triangle ABC$ and the cevian triangle $\triangle P_aP_bP_c$, where P_a, P_b, P_c are the cevians of P with respect to $\triangle ABC$.

By analogy with the Cartesian formula, we instead define the polar of $P(u, v, w)$ relative to $\triangle ABC$ as the line

$$ux + vy + wz = 0.$$

In this formulation, $\triangle ABC$ is self-polar: each side of the triangle is the polar of its opposite vertex. The polar intersects the sides BC, CA, AB at points P''_a, P''_b, P''_c , which are reflections of P'_a, P'_b, P'_c across the midpoints M_1, M_2, M_3 of BC, CA, AB , respectively. Here P'_a, P'_b, P'_c denote the intersections of the Desargues axis of perspectivity with the sides BC, CA, AB .

The *inverse image* P' of a point $P(u, v, w)$ relative to $\triangle ABC$ is defined as the intersection of the line GP with the polar of P , where G is the centroid of $\triangle ABC$. Its barycentric coordinates are

$$P' = (v^2 + w^2 - u(v + w), u^2 + w^2 - v(u + w), u^2 + v^2 - w(u + v)).$$

Figure 19: Geometric configuration for triangle polarity and inversion.

This inversion corresponds to inversion with respect to a conic \mathcal{S} of negative power. Moreover, \mathcal{S} is a scaled version of the Steiner circumellipse \mathcal{S}_c centered at G , with scaling ratio $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$. Under this inversion, the Steiner circumellipse \mathcal{S}_c and the Steiner inellipse \mathcal{S}_i are interchanged. However, the Steiner inellipse \mathcal{S}_i is also the nine point conic for the four points A, B, C and G the centroid. Observe, that this aligns with our knowledge of polar circle inversion as it interchanges the nine point circle with the circumcircle.

7.2 Affine Normalization and the Circular Model of Triangle Inversion

A key structural observation is that the geometry underlying triangle polarity and triangle inversion becomes especially transparent after an affine normalization of the reference triangle. Since any nondegenerate triangle is affinely equivalent to an equilateral triangle, there exists an affine transformation

$$T : \mathbb{R}^2 \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$$

such that

$$T(A) = A', \quad T(B) = B', \quad T(C) = C',$$

where $\triangle A'B'C'$ is equilateral. Because affine maps preserve lines, parallelism, and the class of conics, this normalization allows us to reinterpret the barycentric constructions in a Euclidean setting without loss of generality.

Under the map T , the centroid G of $\triangle ABC$ is sent to the centroid G' of the equilateral triangle $\triangle A'B'C'$. Likewise, the Steiner circumellipse \mathcal{S}_c of $\triangle ABC$ is mapped to the Steiner circumellipse of $\triangle A'B'C'$. For an equilateral triangle, however, the Steiner circumellipse coincides with the circumcircle. Consequently,

$$T(\mathcal{S}_c) = \text{circumcircle of } \triangle A'B'C'.$$

If \mathcal{S} denotes the conic used to define triangle inversion—namely, the homothetic image of \mathcal{S}_c from G with ratio $1/\sqrt{2}$ —then T maps \mathcal{S} to a concentric circle of radius scaled by the same factor:

$$T(\mathcal{S}) = \text{circle centered at } G' \text{ with radius } \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}R,$$

where R is the circumradius of $\triangle A'B'C'$.

In this normalized model, the polarity defined by the equation

$$ux + vy + wz = 0$$

becomes the usual polar line of the point $T(P)$ with respect to the circle $T(\mathcal{S})$. Likewise, the inversion map

$$P \mapsto P' = GP \cap \text{polar}(P)$$

is transformed into ordinary Euclidean circle inversion with respect to $T(\mathcal{S})$, centered at G' . Thus, triangle inversion is projectively equivalent to classical circle inversion, with the affine normalization providing the bridge between the barycentric and Euclidean viewpoints.

This perspective clarifies the geometric meaning of the inversion formula

$$P' = (v^2 + w^2 - u(v + w), u^2 + w^2 - v(u + w), u^2 + v^2 - w(u + v)),$$

which is precisely the barycentric expression of circle inversion in the normalized model, pulled back through the affine map T^{-1} . The entire structure of triangle polarity and inversion therefore arises as the projective image of familiar Euclidean inversion.

7.3 Generalization of Polar Inversion

Let $P = (p, q, r)$ and $D = (u, v, w)$. We define the P -polar line of the point D with respect to the reference triangle $\triangle ABC$ as the line

$$\ell_P(D): uqrx + vpry + wpqz = 0.$$

The inverse image of D under the P -polar inversion relative to $\triangle ABC$ is defined to be the point D' , given by the intersection of the line PD with the P -polar line $\ell_P(D)$.

The barycentric coordinates of D' are $D' = (x, y, z)$, where

$$\begin{aligned} x &:= p^2qw^2 + p^2rv^2 - pqrwv - pqrwu, \\ y &:= pq^2w^2 + q^2ru^2 - pqrwv - pqrvu, \\ z &:= pr^2v^2 + qr^2u^2 - pqrwv - pqrwu. \end{aligned}$$

The P -polar inversion induces a specific geometry relative to the point P . We define the three fundamental conics associated with this transformation: the Conic of Inversion (generalizing the Polar Circle), the P -Circumconic, and the P -Nine-Point Conic.

1. The P -Polar Conic (Conic of Inversion)

This is the locus of points that lie on their own P -polar line. It generalizes the Polar Circle.

- **Equation:**

$$\mathcal{K}_P: \quad qrx^2 + pry^2 + pqz^2 = 0$$

(Dividing by pqr , this takes the diagonal form $\frac{x^2}{p} + \frac{y^2}{q} + \frac{z^2}{r} = 0$).

- **Center:** The center of \mathcal{K}_P is the point $P(p : q : r)$.
- **Note:** When P is the orthocenter H (with coordinates $p = 1/S_A$, etc.), this becomes the standard Polar Circle equation $\sum S_A x^2 = 0$.

2. The P -Circumconic

This is the unique conic passing through the vertices A, B, C that corresponds to the Circumcircle in the geometry of P . It is the isogonal conjugate of the line at infinity with respect to the metric induced by P .

- **Equation:**

$$\mathcal{C}_P : p(q+r)yz + q(r+p)zx + r(p+q)xy = 0$$

- **Center (O_P):** The center of this conic is given by:

$$O_P = (q+r : r+p : p+q)$$

(When $P = H$, $q+r = \frac{1}{s_B} + \frac{1}{s_C} \propto a^2 S_A$, which yields the classical Circumcenter O).

3. The P -Nine-Point Conic

This conic passes through the midpoints of the sides of $\triangle ABC$ and the midpoints of the segments PA, PB, PC . It is the image of the P -Circumconic under the homothety $h(P, 1/2)$.

- **Center (N_P):** The center of the P -Nine-Point Conic is the midpoint of the segment PO_P . Its coordinates are:

$$N_P = (2p+q+r : p+2q+r : p+q+2r)$$

- **Relation to Inversion:** The P -polar inversion swaps the P -Circumconic \mathcal{C}_P and the P -Nine-Point Conic \mathcal{N}_P .

The P -polar inversion is an involutive transformation that:

1. Fixes the P -Polar Conic \mathcal{K}_P pointwise.
2. Maps the P -Circumconic \mathcal{C}_P to the P -Nine-Point Conic \mathcal{N}_P .

References

- [1] Khayou, H., It is all about seeing things in perspective - part I: Solutions to Alhazen's problem and beyond, *International Journal of Geometry*, 15(3)(2026) 58–81.
- [2] Grinberg, D., Begonia theorem in geometry, 2024. Accessed: January 19, 2026.